

Novel Stability Indicating RP-UPLC Method Development and Validation for The Quantification of Nefopam Hydrochloride in Tablet Dosage Form and Characterization of Its Degradation Products

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ABSTRACT

A novel stability indicating RP-UPLC method has been developed for the estimation of Nefopam hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. The Chromatographic separation was achieved on C18 (4.6 mm * 100 mm; 3 microns) column using the mobile phase buffer: acetonitrile: methanol in the ratio of 50:41:9 at a flow rate of 0.6 ml/min. The detection wavelength was 225 nm. Linearity was obeyed in the concentration of 22.63 µg/ml to 67.90 µg/ml. The recovery of Nefopam was found to be 99.72 %. In precision study % RSD was found to be 0.47 for repeatability and 0.60 % for intermediate precision. By using the developed method, percentage label claim of marketed formulation was found to be 100.39%. Forced degradation studies showed significant degradation under Acid hydrolysis. This UPLC method is suitable for routine quality control of Nefopam hydrochloride in pharmaceutical formulation, effectively distinguishing degradation products and ensuring regulatory compliance.

Keywords: Nefopam hydrochloride, NSAID, Validation, ICH guidelines, Forced degradation, stability indicating method.

INTRODUCTION

Nefopam hydrochloride ((±) – 3,4,5,6 – tetra hydro – 5-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-2, 5-benzoxazocine hydrochloride) is a non-opioid analgesic and anti-inflammatory agent, chemically similar to the Orphenadrine [1]. It is widely used for the relief of moderate to severe pain. It is a white crystalline powder with an aqueous solubility of approximately 43.5 µg/ml at room temperature. It has log P of 3.16 and pK_a of 9 [2]. Nefopam is metabolized by N-demethylation [3]. Nefopam inhibits the reuptake of serotonin, norepinephrine and dopamine. It also

reduces glutamate signaling via modulating sodium and calcium channels [4]. Literature review revealed that Spectrophotometry [5-7], Thin Layer Chromatography [8], High Performance Liquid Chromatography [9-11], Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry [12] and Gas Chromatography [13] methods have been developed for the quantification of Nefopam hydrochloride. Objective of the current study was to develop a novel stability indicating RP – UPLC method for the quantitative determination of Nefopam hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form as per ICH guidelines [14].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents

Nefopam hydrochloride standard was procured from Synthiya research laboratory, Pondicherry. Nefopam hydrochloride tablets (Nefosar-30 mg) were received as a gift sample from Crescent Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Methanol HPLC grade, Acetonitrile HPLC grade, Triethylamine AR grade, and Orthophosphoric acid AR grade were obtained from Merck India Limited, Mumbai, and used for the preparation of mobile phase.

Instrumentation

Shimadzu UV/VIS spectrophotometer with lab solution software was used for all the spectrophotometric measurements. The chromatographic estimation was performed on Agilent-1220 infinity UPLC system using Chemstation software. For pH adjustment of the solution, the Lab India pH meter was employed. Shimadzu balance was employed for weighing the samples.

Diluent

Based up on the solubility of the drug, the diluent was selected. Buffer, acetonitrile and methanol were taken in the ratio of 50:41:9.

Preparation of standard stock solution

30 mg of Nefopam hydrochloride was accurately weighed and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Three-fourths of the diluent was added and sonicated for 10 minutes. The solution was made up to volume with diluent and labeled as standard stock solution.

Preparation of standard working solution (100% solution)

3.0 ml of Nefopam hydrochloride from the standard stock solution was pipetted into a 20.0ml volumetric flask and made up to volume with diluent.

Preparation of sample stock solution

Twenty tablets accurately weighed and the average weight of each tablet was calculated. Weight equivalent to 30 mg was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. 50 ml of diluent was added and the

solution was sonicated for 25 minutes. The volume was then made up to 100 ml with diluent and filtered through 0.45 μ syringe filters.

Preparation of sample working solution (100% solution)

3.0 ml of the filtered sample stock solution was transferred to a 20.0ml volumetric flask and made up to volume with diluent.

Preparation of buffer

2 ml of triethylamine was added to 500ml of HPLC water and the pH was adjusted to 2.8 using OPA.

Method development

Based on the drug solubility and pK_a value, the following conditions have been used to develop the method for the estimation of Nefopam hydrochloride.

Optimized chromatographic conditions

Column: C₁₈; (4.6 mm * 100 mm); 3 microns

Mobile phase: Buffer: Acetonitrile: Methanol (50:41:9)

Buffer: 2 ml of triethylamine in 500ml of water, and pH adjusted to 2.8 using OPA.

Flow rate: 0.6 ml/min

Detector: 225 nm

Temperature: 30°C

Injection volume: 5 μ l

Specificity

Specificity is the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be present. Typically these might include excipients, impurities, degradants, etc. lack of specificity of an individual analytical procedure may be compensated by other supporting analytical procedure [14].

Linearity and Range

The linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability (within a given range) to obtain test results that are

directly proportional to the concentration of analyte in the sample[14].

Accuracy

Twenty tablets was accurately weighed and average weight of each tablet was calculated. Then, a weigh equivalent to 30 mg was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask. 50 ml of diluent was added and the solution was sonicated for 20 minutes. The volume was made up with the diluent and filtered through 0.45 μ syringe filters.

Acceptance criteria

The percentage recovery of each level should lie between 98.0 to 102% [14-26].

Precision

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions. Precision may be considered at three levels: Repeatability, intermediate precision, and reproducibility. The precision of an analytical procedure is usually expressed as the variance, standard deviations, or coefficient of variation of a series of measurements [14].

Robustness

Small deliberate changes in the method like flow rate, mobile phase ratio and temperature were made. However there was no significant change in the results, and all values remained within the range of ICH guidelines. Robustness conditions like flow minus (0.5 ml/min), flow plus (0.7 ml/min), wave length plus (226 nm) and wavelength minus (224 nm) were maintained and the samples were injected in duplicate. System suitability parameters was not significantly affected and %RSD remained within the acceptable limit.

LOD & LOQ

LOD & LOQ were calculated separately using the calibration curve method. The LOD and LOQ of the compound were determined using the developed UPLC method by injecting progressively lower concentrations of the standard solution.

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDIES

Alkali degradation

3 ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 20 ml standard volumetric flask, to this solution 0.1 M sodium hydroxide was added at a temperature conditions of 35°C and it is left for 2 hours. Then a small quantity of 1ml of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid was added as in process to neutralize and it was then made up to the mark using mobile phase (diluent). The sample as taken after 24hrs and then subjected in UPLC for peak estimation.

Acid degradation

3 ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 20 ml standard volumetric flask, to this solution 0.1M hydrochloric acid was added and it is left for 2 hours. Then 1 ml of 0.1 M sodium hydroxide was added to neutralize and it was then made up to the mark using mobile phase (diluent). The sample was taken after 24hrs and then injected in UPLC for peak estimation.

Oxidation degradation

The forced degradation of Nefopam hydrochloride was studied under the influence of 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). 3 ml of sample stock solution is taken in a 20 ml standard volumetric flask and then 2 ml of 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) as added and left for a time of 2 hours under 35°C temperature. Then the diluent was added and it was made up to the volume and the sample was subjected to UPLC run after 24hr.

Thermal degradation

30 mg of Nefopam hydrochloride was accurately weighed and then it was subjected to heat at 105°C for 6 hrs. Then this sample was taken into the 100 ml standard flask and made up the volume with mobile phase. From the above solution 3 ml was taken into the 20 ml volumetric flask and made up to the volume with mobile phase then subjected to UPLC run after 24 hrs.

Photo-stability study

30 mg of Nefopam hydrochloride was accurately weighed and then it was subjected to UV radiation at 254 and 365 nm for one week. Then this sample was

taken into a 100 ml standard flask and made up the volume with mobile phase. From the above solution 3 ml was taken into a 20 ml volumetric flask and made up to the volume with mobile phase. It was then subjected to UPLC run after 24 hrs.

Characterization of degradation products

The forced degradation product was subjected to spectroscopic and chromatographic studies. The UV, IR, NMR and Mass spectra of degradation product were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Linearity

To demonstrate the linearity of the assay method, inject 6 standard solutions with concentrations ranging from 22.63 ppm to 67.90 ppm of Nefopam hydrochloride. Plot a graph of concentration versus peak area, and correlation co-efficient was found to be 1.000.

Accuracy

Three concentrations of 80%, 100% and 150% were injected in triplicate manner and % recovery was calculated as 99.72% (Table I).

Table 1. Accuracy data of Nefopam hydrochloride

% level	Sample wt. (mg)	Area	Content (mg)	Content (%)
80%	174.35	657.582	29.849	99.50
	173.65	656.870	29.937	99.79
	175.55	655.822	29.566	98.55
100%	216.89	821.118	29.962	99.87
	216.38	818.532	29.938	99.79
	216.98	824.316	30.066	100.22
150%	259.36	983.982	30.025	100.08
	258.89	983.387	30.062	100.21
	261.01	983.886	29.833	99.44

Precision

Six working sample solution of 45ppm were injected and the percentage amount was calculated. The % RSD was found to be 0.47 (Table II).

Repeatability

Table 2. Repeatability data of Nefopam hydrochloride

S.No.	Sample ID	Sample weight (mg)	Area	Content (mg)	% Assay
1	Sample 1	215.35	835.562	30.161	100.29
2	Sample 2	216.65	833.608	29.909	99.61
3	Sample 3	214.48	831.992	30.154	99.62
4	Sample 4	215.11	836.276	30.220	99.86
5	Sample 5	213.89	834.077	30.312	99.67
6	Sample 6	216.01	834.591	30.033	101.13
Mean				30.132	100.44
SD				0.142	0.472
%RSD				0.47	0.47

Intermediate precision

Six working sample solutions of 45ppm are injected on the next day of the preparation of samples, and the % amount found was calculated. The % RSD was found to be 0.60

LOD

Detection limit of Nefopam hydrochloride in this method was found to be 0.02 µg/ml.

LOQ

Quantification limit of Nefopam hydrochloride in this method was found to be 0.06 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Robustness

Small deliberate changes in this method were made, such as flow minus, flow plus, wave length plus and wavelength minus and the %RSD under these conditions was calculated.

Assay of marketed formulation

Standard solution (Fig. 1) and sample solution were injected separately into the system and chromatograms were recorded, and drug present in the sample was calculated.

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of Nefopam hydrochloride standard

System suitability

A standard solution of Nefopam hydrochloride working standard was prepared as per procedure and injected six times into the UPLC system. The system suitability parameters were evaluated from standard chromatograms obtained by calculating the % RSD of retention time, tailing factor, theoretical plates and

peak areas from six replicate injections and were found to be within the range.

Forced degradation studies

The degradation of Nefopam hydrochloride in various stress condition was performed and their results were presented in Table III. Nefopam was found to degrade by acid hydrolysis.

Table 3. Degradation studies report

Stress condition		Temperature	% Active substances
Alkali degradation (0.1 M NaOH)		35°C	100.15
Acid degradation (0.1 M HCl)		125°C	90.05
Oxidative degradation (3% H ₂ O ₂)		35°C	100.85
Thermal degradation		105°C	100.28
Photolytic degradation	At 254 nm	35°C	100.31
	At 365 nm	35°C	99.95

Fig. 2. Alkali degradation spectrum of Nefopam hydrochloride

Fig. 3. Acid degradation spectrum of Nefopam hydrochloride

Fig. 4. Oxidative degradation spectrum of Nefopam hydrochloride

Fig. 5. Thermal degradation spectrum of Nefopam hydrochloride

Fig. 6. Photolytic degradation spectrum of Nefopam hydrochloride (at 254nm)

Fig. 7. Photolytic degradation spectrum of Nefopam hydrochloride (at 365nm)

Fig. 8. UV spectrum of degradation of product of NEF

Fig. 9. IR spectrum of degradation of product of NEF

Fig. 10. NMR spectrum of degradation of product of NEF

Fig. 11. Mass spectrum of degradation of product of NEF

Fig. 12. Probable degradation pathway of NEF

Toxicity prediction

The chemical structure was drawn in OSIRIS property explorer to show the biological properties of the compound. Properties like high risks of undesired effects like mutagenicity, tumorigenicity and reproductive effect are shown in red, green color

indicated the drug conform behavior. It was found that the degraded product is mutagenic, tumorigenic and has no irritability and reproductive effects as shown in Figure-. 27

Fig. 13. Toxicity prediction of degradation product of NEF by acid hydrolysis

CONCLUSION

A novel stability indicating RP- UPLC method was developed for the estimation of Nefopam hydrochloride in pharmaceutical dosage form. The method was optimized by evaluating various chromatographic conditions. Sample recovery was in good agreement with the respective label claim. The forced degradation product was characterized by various analytical techniques. Since the developed method is able to quantify Nefopam hydrochloride in presence of its degradation product so the method is stability indicating. The proposed method was validated as per ICH guidelines across all relevant parameters. This method can be effectively used for quality control testing of NSAID drug Nefopam hydrochloride in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

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